

“A Study To Assess The Effectiveness Of Health Education On Knowledge Regarding Eating Disorder Among The College Girls On Selected Technical College Of Jabalpur, (M.P.)”

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ABSTRACT:

Eating disorders are mental health disorders, they affect physical, mental and behavioral condition. Eating disorder are behavioural condition characterized by severe and persistent disturbance in eating behavior and associated distressing thoughts and emotions. It is described as abnormal .They can be very serious conditions affecting physical, psychological and social function. Types of eating disorder include Anorexia nervosa, Bulimia nervosa and binge eating disorder. Eating disorder affect several million people at any given time, most often women between the age of 12-35. The conceptual framework used for this study. Tool used was questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge regarding eating disorder among college girls. Data were collected from selected technical college of Jabalpur after getting permission from the college authority. For this study the researcher select 60 samples by using non-probability convenience sampling technique after getting written consent for subject. The data was collected, time spent for conduct health education was approximately 45 minutes.

Analysis revealed that there was marked increase in theme an value from 11.29 in the pre-test to 18.81 in post-test and the standard deviation is increased from 5.51 in pre-test to 5.46 in the posttest. The mean difference was 7.52 and the calculated 't' value was 7.59 and table value at 0.05 level is 2.00, calculated value was more than table value (7.59 > 2.00) at significant level (0.05). So alternative hypothesis was accepted. the statistically high significant difference between the pre and post-test level of knowledge. Hence it indicates health education was effective.

Keywords- Assess, Health Education, Effectiveness, Knowledge, Eating Disorder, College, College girls

INTRODUCTION

Conducted a survey in 2015 which found that around 2% of the Indian population suffers from eating disorders. Another study conducted in 2018 found that eating disorder affected 6.5% of adolescent girl in India. Apart from these survey in 2023 studies by licensed therapists across the country state that, eating disorders affect an estimated 2-3% of the India population, with a higher incidence among women. Anorexia nervosa, Bulimia. nervosa, Binge-eating disorder are the

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most commonly diagnosed eating disorders in India.

According to world health organization, 2023 studies have determined that 2.7% of teens will experience an eating disorder in their lifetime 13% of adolescents will develop an eating disorder by the age of 20 3.8% of female, and 1.5% of male, adolescents will struggle with an eating disorder.

In India 2023 a survey reports shows that the lack of knowledge about eating disorders, with 59.4% and 39.8% of adolescents. Types of eating disorder include Anorexia nervosa, Bulimia nervosa and binge eating disorder. Taken together, eating disorders affect up to 5% of the population, most often develop in adolescents and young adulthood. Behaviours associated with eating disorders including restrictive eating or binge eating, purging by vomiting or laxative, diuretics misuse or compulsive exercise. These behaviours can become driven in ways that appear similar to an addiction. Eating disorders often co-occur with other psychiatric disorders most commonly, mood and anxiety disorders, obsessive-compulsive disorder, and alcohol and substance use disorders.

OBJECTIVES -

1. Assess the pre-test knowledge regarding eating disorder among the college girls on selected technical college of Jabalpur.
2. Assess the post-test knowledge regarding eating disorder among the college girls on selected technical college of Jabalpur.
3. Assess the effectiveness of health education regarding eating disorder among the college girls on selected technical college of Jabalpur.
4. Determine the association between the pre-test knowledge score with selected demographic variables.

HYPOTHESES

H1- There will be significant mean difference between pre-test and post-test knowledge regarding eating disorder among college girls on selected technical college of Jabalpur.

H2- There will be significant association between pre test knowledge score of college girls with their selected demographic variables.

METHODOLOGY

This pre-experimental study was conducted in selected technical College of Jabalpur. The conceptual framework used for this study. Tool used was questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge regarding eating disorder among college girls. Data were collected from selected technical college of Jabalpur after getting permission from the college authority. For this study the researcher select 60 samples by using non-probability convenience sampling

technique after getting written consent for subject. The data was collected, time spent for conduct health education was approximately 45 minutes.

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. College girls who are studying at selected technical college of Jabalpur (M.P.).
2. College girls above 18years.
3. College girls who are able to read, speak and understand Hindi and English.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. College girls who are absent at the time of data collection.
2. Those college girls who are not willing to participate in study.

TOOL DESCRIPTION:-

The tool used in this study is the self-structured questionnaire. It constructed by the investigator consist of two sections –

Section A: Consists of socio-demographic variables which consists of 8 items: Age, residence, type of family, number of siblings, monthly family income, dietary habit, source of information, medical history of eating disorder.

Section B: Consists of self-structured questionnaire regarding eating disorder. self-structured questionnaire as 30 questions. It has prepared as multiple-choice questions for assessing the knowledge of college girls regarding eating disorder.

SCORING CRITERIA

knowledge score - A score of 0-10 poor, a score of 11-20 average, a score 21-30 good.

S.NO.	LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	SCORING
1.	POOR	0-10
2.	AVERAGE	11-20
3.	GOOD	21-30

Table- 1 Representation of scoring criteria

RESULT / MAJOR -FINDINGS

Analysis revealed that there was marked increase in the mean value from 11.29 in the pre-test to 18.81 in post-test and the standard deviation is increased from 5.51 in pre-test to 5.46 in the post test. The mean difference was 7.52 and the calculated 't' value was 7.59 and table value at 0.05 level is 2.00, calculated value was more than table value (7.59>2.00)

at significant level (0.05). So alternative hypothesis was accepted. The statistically high significant difference between the pre and post-test level of knowledge. Hence it indicates health education was effective.

Section I Demographic distribution from the major findings, the majority of 60 samples. It was relieved that college girls maximum 40 (66.67%) are in the age group of 18-20 years, 18 (30%) are in the age group of 21-22 years, 2 (3.33%) are in the age group of 23-25 years, 0(0%) are in the age group of 25 year or above.

Maximum 35 (58.33%) , from urban ,22 (36.67%) from rural 3 (5%) from sub urban.

Maximum 32 (53.33%) , from nuclear family ,26 (43.33%) from joint family,2 (3.34%) from extended family. Out of 60 college girls 23(38.34%) have 2 siblings, 20 (33.33%) have 1sibling,15 (25%) have more than 2 siblings ,2 (3.33%) have 0 sibling. Out of 60 college girls 20 (33.33%) have 10,000-20,000 monthly family income, 17

(28.33%) have less than 10,000 monthly family income, 12 (20%) have more than 30,000 monthly family income, 11 (18.34%) have 20,000-30,000 monthly family income. Maximum 44 (73.33%) are vegetarian,10 (16.67%) are eggetarian,6 (10%) are non-vegetarian.

Out of 60 college girls 40 (66.67%) have no information, 15 (25%) have source of information from radio and television ,5 (8.33%) have source of information from family, friends and health care personnel, magazines and newspapers, 0 (0%) have any other source of information. Maximum 55 (91.67%) no any history of eating disorders, 3 (5%) have any other type of eating disorders, 2 (3.33%) have medical history of bulimia nervosa, 0 (0%) have medical history of anorexia nervosa.

SECTION-I

DISTRIBUTIONS OF COLLEGE GIRLS, ACCORDING TO THEIR PRE-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE ON EATING DISORDER.

N = 60

S.NO.	TEST	GRADE	F	%	MEAN	SD
1.	Pretest	Poor	25	41.7%	11.29	5.51
		Average	34	56.7%		
		Good	1	1.6%		

TABLE NO. 2 GRADE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE, MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF PRE-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF COLLEGE GIRL

N=60

S.NO.	TEST	GRADE	F	%	MEAN	SD
1.	Post-test	Poor	2	3.33%	18.81	5.46
		Average	36	60%		

		Good	22	36.67%		
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GRADE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE, MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF PRE-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF COLLEGE GIRLS

FIGURE 1- Depicts that grade wise distribution of pre-test knowledge score of college girl .In pre-test 34 (56.7%) college girls have average knowledge,25 (41.7%) have good knowledge and 1 (1.6%) have poor knowledge.

The mean knowledge score of pre-tests of college girls is 11.29 with standard deviation 5.51. Table reveals that there is gain in knowledge score. Now the objective 1 is fulfilled.

SECTION-II

DISTRIBUTIONS OF COLLEGE, GIRLS ACCORDING TO THEIR POST-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE ON EATING DISORDER.

TABLE- NO. 3 GRADE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE, MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF POST-TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF COLLEGE GIRLS

FIGURE 2- Depicts that grade wise distribution of pre-test knowledge score of college girls. In post-test 36 (60%) college girls have average knowledge,22 (36.67%) have good knowledge and 2 (3.33%) have poor knowledge. The mean knowledge score of post-tests of college girls is 18.81with standard deviation 5.46 Table reveals that there is gain in knowledge score. Now the objective 2 is fulfilled.

SECTION-III

ANALYSIS OF EFFECTIVE OF HEALTH EDUCATION ON KNOWLEDGE REGARDING EATING DISORDER AMONG COLLEGE GIRLS

TABLE NO. 4 SIGNIFICANCE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN PRE AND POST TEST KNOWLEDGE SCORE OF COLLEGE GIRLS BY USING 't' TEST.

N = 60

S.N O.	TEST	MEAN SCORE	MEAN DIFFERENCE	SD	SD DIFFERENCE	't' VALUE	INFERENCE
01	PRE-TEST	11.29	7.52	5.51	0.05	7.59	Significant
02	POST-TEST	18.81		5.46			

Table value =2.00

FIGURE 3- Depicts that the mean knowledge score of pre-test is

11.29 and the mean knowledge score of post-test is 18.81, mean difference of pre-test and post-test is 7.52 with standard deviation of pre-test is 5.51, standard deviation of post-test is 5.46, SD difference of pre-test and post-test is 0.05 and calculated 't' value is 7.59 since the table value at 0.05 level is 2.00 and calculated 't' value is 7.59.

Hence H1 is accepted - There is significant difference between mean pre-test and post-test knowledge score regarding eating disorder among college girls.

SECTION-IV

ASSOCIATION:-

Section IV association of each variable with level of pre-test knowledge score on the association of pre-test knowledge with the demographic variable, it was found that age (chi value 0.879), residence (chi value 1.596), Type of family (chi value 11.875), no. Of siblings (chi value 34.155), monthly family income (chi value 7.52), dietary habits (chi value 1.1367) source of information (chi value 7.304), medical history of eating disorders (chi value 20.412), regarding eating disorder are having or not significant relation with pre-test knowledge score. The study findings showed that a most significant is no. of siblings and significant with selected variable that type of family, medical history of eating disorders and other variable are such as age, residence, monthly income, dietary habits, source of information was not significant. So, hypothesis H₂ was accepted.

Thus, the hypothesis made by the investigator that there will be significant association between the pre-test knowledge score with selected demographic variable at the level of $p < 0.05$ are accepted.

LIMITATIONS-

1. The study was confined to selected technical college of Jabalpur which limits the generalization of the findings.
2. Sample size only 60 and hence finding could not be generalized to all college girls.

CONCLUSION

Pre-test knowledge score of college girls. In pre-test 34(56.7%) college girls have average knowledge, 25(41.7%) have good knowledge and 1 (1.6%) have poor knowledge. The mean knowledge score of pre-tests of college girls is 11.29 with standard deviation 5.51. Table reveals that there is gain in knowledge score. Now the objective 1 is fulfilled.

Health education is an effective method in improving the knowledge on eating disorder. Knowledge on eating disorder will help in the prevention of eating disorder and thereby reduce the mortality and morbidity. Health

education also create a desire to know more about the eating disorder and other mental health related disorders. There was significant association between the pretest knowledge score of college girls on eating disorder with their selected demographic variables.

REFERENCES-

- Malik Santosh, text book of psychiatric nursing, unit 5, 3rd edition, published by Rajinder kapoor, lotus publishers, page no. 195-200.
- T. Anbu, text book of psychiatric nursing, chapter 10, 3rd edition, published by s. Hegde, emmess medical publishers page no. 283-290.
- R sreevani, a guide to mental health and psychiatric nursing, chapter 10, S4th edition, jaypee brothers medical publishers(p).ltd. Page no. 270-273.
- P.prakash, text book of mental health and psychiatric nursing, chapter 11, 1st edition, published by satish kumar jain, cbs publishers and distributors Pvt. Ltd. Page no. 298-302.

<https://nerb.gov.in/en/node/3722>

<https://www.ijcmph.com>

<https://www.researchgate.net>

<https://www.worldwidejournals.com>